

Hormone Replacement Therapy in the Diagnosis and Intervention of Postmenopausal Osteoporosis

Rahul Anshuman¹, Amrita²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopedics, NSMCH, Patna, Bihar, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 15-04-2022 / Revised: 20-05-2022 / Accepted: 05-06-2022

Corresponding author: Dr Rahul Anshuman

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Reducing the frequency of vertebral and non-vertebral fractures (particularly at the hip), which are to blame for the morbidity associated with the illness, is the goal of treatment for postmenopausal osteoporosis. In early postmenopausal women, hormone replacement therapy is still an important tool for osteoporosis prevention. At various doses, hormone replacement treatment (HRT) quickly restores bone turnover and preserves bone mineral density (BMD) at all skeletal locations, resulting in a marked decline in both vertebral and nonvertebral fractures. A one-year follow-up was done by 84 postmenopausal women who were randomly assigned to one of four groups. The first group (n = 20) received conjugated estrogens (CE; 25 days/month) at a rate of 0.625 mg/day. The third (n = 17) received 50 µg/day of transdermal 179-estradiol cyclically (24 days/month) while the second (n = 23) received 0.625 mg/day of CE continuously. The fourth group (n = 24) served as a treatment-free control group, whereas all of these groups additionally received 2.5 mg of medroxyprogesterone acetate consecutively throughout the final 12 days of hormone replacement therapy. Dual photon absorptiometry was performed prior to treatment and again after a year. Prior to treatment and six and twelve months later, measurements of serum calcium, phosphate, and osteocalcin levels as well as urinary calcium/creatinine and hydroxyproline/creatinine ratios were made. The amount of bone mineral increased across the board in all treatment groups. This rise was greater in the transdermal group (7.1 percent, P <0.01) and the continuous CE therapy group (4.4 percent, P <0.05). Concomitant biochemical effects at 6 and 12 months, including decreases in blood calcium, phosphate, and osteocalcin, as well as decreases in urine calcium and hydroxyproline, were consistent with the effects on bone mineral reported.

Keywords: Hormone Replacement Therapy, Osteoporosis, Postmenopausal, Prevention, Treatment

This is an Open Access article that uses a fund-ing model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Background

Women's bone mass essentially stays constant up until menopause. The amount of bone mineral starts to decrease as soon as ovarian activity stops, and fractures become more common [1-3]. Additionally,

premenopausal and perimenopausal women's bone mass is dramatically decreased by bilateral oophorectomy [4,5]. However, despite the numerous studies demonstrating the preventive impact of

estrogens against bone loss during the menopause, it is also well known that once oestrogen therapy is discontinued, the process is reactivated [6,9,10]. The majority of these studies [11,12] evaluate the effectiveness of the dosage and the treatment. This study compares the effects of various hormone replacement therapy regimens and delivery methods on bone metabolism.

Materials and Methods

Patients

To take part in the study, 99 healthy women with recent menopause (less than 24 months) and early menopause (younger than 50 years old) who had not used any kind of sex hormone replacement treatment were required. 84 of the study's 99 postmenopausal participants finished the 1-year follow-up. Patients were divided into one of four groups at random:

Group 1: (n = 20) conjugated equine estrogen cyclically 0.625 mg/day (24 days/month).

Group 2: (n = 23) conjugated equine estrogen continuously 0.625 mg/day (each day/month).

Group 3: (n = 17) transdermal 17 α -estradiol cyclically. 50 mg/day (24 days/month).

Group 4: (n = 24) free-treatment control group. All treated groups received 2.5 mg of medroxyprogesterone acetate (MPA) sequentially for the last 12 days of estrogen therapy.

Analysis

In 2-h samples, urine calcium, creatinine, and hydroxyproline were measured [13]. The morning following an overnight fast and cigarette abstinence, blood samples were obtained. The measurement of creatinine used picric acid photolorimetry. The ultrafiltered sample was converted to phenyl isothiocyanate

before being subjected to high-resolution liquid chromatography analysis to measure the amount of hydroxyproline (Waters, Millipore Corp., Milford, MA, USA). Atomic absorption techniques were used to measure calcium in urine, while orthocresolphthalein photolorimetry was used to measure calcium in serum. Using molybdate ammonium photolorimetry and UV light, serum phosphate was quantified. All prior measurements were adjusted to a discontinuous flow auto-analyzer, with the exception of urine calcium and hydroxyproline. Serum osteocalcin was determined by radioimmunoassay. Basal, 6-month and twelve-month samples were taken.

Bone mass measurement

Dual photon absorptiometry was used to compare the lumbar spine's (L2-L4) bone mineral density before and after treatment (at 12 months) (Lunar DP3 system). Precision (<3%) and radiation exposure (<10 mrem) are both excellent. Because age margins were small and remarkably consistent across all four groups, no age-matched values were employed.

Statistical analysis

The mean + S.D. was used to express the results. Pairwise Student's *t*-test was used to determine statistical differences between baseline and treatment values within the groups, and analysis of variance was used to investigate differences between the groups. Wilcoxon and Kruskal-Wallis ranked-pairs tests were applied where needed. $P < 0.05$ was deemed significant. The Statistical Analysis Package was used to analyse the results (Walonick Ass., Minneapolis, USA).

Results

15 of the 99 participants that were referred for the study withdrew. In Table I, the causes of default are listed.

Table 1: Reasons for Defaulting From Study

Reason	Group	n
Abnormal uterine bleeding	Continuous CEE	3
Erythema in patch application area	Transdermal	3
Poor relief of climacteric symptoms	Transdermal	2
	Cyclic CEE	3
Endometrial hyperplasia	Cyclic CEE	2
	Transdermal	3

Clinical parameters (Table II) and baseline results did not show significant differences between the four studied groups.

Table 2: Clinical data

Group	n	Age (years)	Mean elapsed time since menopause (mcinths)	Weight (kgs)
1	21	45.1 + 6.3	20.7 + 14.3	66.0 + 3.5
2	22	47.4 + 4.3	17.3 + 11.9	68.2 + 4.6
3	18	45.6 + 7.7	23.3 + 22.2	63.3 + 6.9
4	24	49.3 + 2.4	17.1 + 9.8	63.2 + 7.3

After 6 months, serum calcium and phosphate levels significantly decreased in all treatment plans, whereas the control group showed no differences. Osteocalcin levels in all replacement therapy groups were considerably lower at the 6-month follow-up, but they rose in the control group (Table III).

Table 3: Urine analysis and Serum Analysis

Urine Analysis				
	Conjugated estrogens		Transdermal	Control
	continuous	cyclical	17 β -estradiol	
Calcium/creatinine				
0	0.166 $\pm$ 0.02	0.174 $\pm$ 0.01	0.173 $\pm$ 0.02	0.175 $\pm$ 0.02
6	0.129 $\pm$ 0.03	0.159 $\pm$ 0.02	0.119 $\pm$ 0.01 **	0.176 $\pm$ 0.01 ^{NS}
12	0.131 $\pm$ 0.05	0.161 $\pm$ 0.02	0.122 $\pm$ 0.01 **	0.198 $\pm$ 0.02 ^{NS}
Hydroxyproline				
0	131.9 $\pm$ 8.8	130.5 $\pm$ 7.6	135.7 $\pm$ 3.6	136.1 $\pm$ 5.1
6	125.6 $\pm$ 9.1 **	128.0 $\pm$ 9.8 ^{NS}	125.8 $\pm$ 8.7 **	140.3 $\pm$ 9.4 ^{NS}
12	127.1 $\pm$ 7.6 *	128.5 $\pm$ 6.7 ^{NS}	127.7 $\pm$ 9.5 **	141.9 $\pm$ 4.9 ^{NS}
Serum Analysis				
	Conjugated estrogens		Transdermal	Control
	continuous	cyclical	17 β -estradiol	
Phosphate				
0	3.91 $\pm$ 0.08	3.82 $\pm$ 0.11	3.78 $\pm$ 0.13	3.63 $\pm$ 0.13
6	3.69 $\pm$ 0.10*	3.63 $\pm$ 0.09 *	3.61 $\pm$ 0.08 *	3.65 $\pm$ 0.14 ^{NS}
12	3.71 $\pm$ 0.06	3.65 $\pm$ 0.08 *	3.67 $\pm$ 0.08 *	3.65 $\pm$ 0.09 ^{NS}
Calcium				
0	9.66 $\pm$ 0.09	9.82 $\pm$ 0.08	9.72 $\pm$ 0.05	9.54 $\pm$ 0.13
6	9.43 $\pm$ 0.09 *	9.50 $\pm$ 0.09	9.43 $\pm$ 0.06 *	9.56 $\pm$ 0.12 ^{NS}
12	9.43 $\pm$ 0.06 *	9.52 $\pm$ 0.08	9.47 $\pm$ 0.08 *	9.59 $\pm$ 0.11 ^{NS}

In all three hormone replacement groups, the levels of calcium, phosphate, and osteocalcin were found to be significantly lower after a year of treatment than at baseline, although they did not differ from values discovered at six months. The increase seen at six months for all metrics was remained present in the control group after a year. When compared to the baseline and 6-month values, this increase in osteocalcin was substantial (Table III). No differences were found among the therapy groups when comparing the changes in osteocalcin levels between groups at 6 months, but there appeared to be a trend toward a significant difference between the treated and control groups ($P < 0.07$). At the 12-month follow-up, this difference became statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

Urinary calcium and hydroxyproline/creatinine ratios displayed a similar pattern to the changes in serum levels (Table III). At the 12-month follow-up, all hormone replacement therapy groups had higher bone mineral content (Table III). As anticipated, the control group, however, displayed a substantial decline ($P < 0.05$). Women on cyclic conjugated estrogens experienced the lowest rise overall, 1.3% (14 mg/cm²), while patients taking a continuous regimen experienced a greater (4.4 percent, 39 mg/cm²) and significantly higher increase ($P < 0.05$) increase. However, individuals who received transdermal treatment saw the greatest gain in bone mass, at 7.1% (71 mg/cm²) ($P < 0.01$). The control group's average bone mass loss was calculated to be 31 mg/cm².

Discussion

The data from the control group show a clear rise in both resorption and formation rates during the first few years following the onset of menopause. While the rise in osteocalcin levels indicates an increase in bone production, the rise in the urinary calcium/creatinine ratio shows a net increase in resorption. The assumption that bone loss occurs in an early stage of

menopause is supported by the increase in these bone turnover rates in our patients with first menopause and densitometric results further support the notion that the age-related decrease of bone mineral content does indeed start at this time.

The optimum strategy is still up for debate, despite the fact that estrogens obviously have a preventive effect against osteoporosis in menopausal women and numerous articles have recommended administering the lowest effective dose. From a therapeutic perspective, it would undoubtedly be extremely interesting to be able to determine the dose and delivery method of the minimal estrogens that can prevent osteoporosis and do not result in hypertrophic changes in the endometrium. Determining the progestin dosage and delivery method that inhibits endometrial proliferation while having minimal effects on lipid metabolism may also be helpful. This dose was established in earlier research at 2.5 mg of medroxyprogesterone acetate and 0.625 mg of conjugated estrogens [12,16]. Progestins are also known to have preventive effects against bone loss [17,19]. These doses were investigated in the current investigation using oral medications, and the effectiveness of continuous vs. cyclic delivery was assessed. Although the dosage of medroxyprogesterone is not the focus of the current investigation, our findings (Table I) show that 2.5 mg of MPA per day is insufficient to prevent endometrial hyperplasia, especially when transdermal estradiol is used.

The Christiansen group argued for the value of ongoing routines [20]. Our data allow us to suggest that continuous medication is more effective because it seems to reduce bone turnover and raise bone mineral content more than intermittent administration. Although cyclic administration causes a modest increase in bone mass (1.3%), this rise is less than the accuracy of the method (3%)

and cannot be definitively linked to the increase. With a cyclical regime, there is no increase in bone mineral content, which conflicts with other authors' findings [21,22].

Percutaneous [23-25] and transdermal [26] estradiol treatment reduced bone loss in postmenopausal women, according to a number of studies. Stevenson [27] did not discover any differences between oral and transdermal hormone replacement treatment in a randomised investigation. Nevertheless, the administration of 50 pg/day of 17 α -estradiol was the most effective pattern in the study subjects, and our data demonstrate the value of the transdermal route in preventing bone loss associated with menopause. The greatest increase in bone mass was seen in this group.

Conclusion

The holy grail compound that can alleviate menopausal symptoms, such as vasomotor symptoms and vaginal dryness, maintain or increase BMD, lower the risk of fractures at all skeletal sites, as well as lower the risk of cardiovascular disease, dementia, genitourinary issues, and breast, endometrial, and ovarian cancer, has not yet been discovered. Routine use of HRT in postmenopausal women is not advised due to the availability of newer and safer medicinal treatments for osteoporosis and its prevention. However, short-term use of HRT, raloxifene, and/or tibolone is currently allowed to reduce symptoms in some postmenopausal women with early menopause or postmenopausal symptoms. Although osteoporosis prevention is an approved indication for estrogen-based hormone therapy, they shouldn't be used as the first line of treatment for asymptomatic women because there are alternatives available. Serum Before beginning any other treatment for the prevention of bone loss, vitamin D deficiency should be ruled out, and appropriate calcium intake should be made before managing osteoporosis. It is particularly intriguing to note the

stabilization of these annual results when compared to values after 6 months, despite the fact that all treatment groups have bone turnover markers that are much lower than baseline levels after 12 months. This supports the idea that the impact of replacement therapy on bone metabolism is greater in the initial months of treatment and then rather stable after that.

References

1. Smith DM, Khairi MRA, Norton I, Johnston CC Jr. Age and activity effects on rate of bone mineral loss. *J. Clin. Invest* 1976; 58:716-721.
2. Richelson LS, Wahner HW, Melton III LJ, Riggs BL Relative contributions of aging and estrogen deficiency to postmenopausal bone loss. *N Engl J Med* 1984; 311: 1273- 1275.
3. Jensen GJ, Christiansen C, Boesen J, Hegedus V, Transbol F. Epidemiology of postmenopausal spinal and long bone fractures: a unifying approach to postmenopausal osteoporosis. *Clin Orthop* 1982; 166:75-81.
4. Palummeri E, Gelmini G, Bonati PA, Bergonzani M, Davoli L. Effect of ovariectomy on bone mass. Transverse study using photon densitometry. *Minerva Ginecol* 1987; 39:607-613.
5. Stepan JJ, Pospichal J, Schreiber V, Kanka I, Mensic I, Presl I, Pacovsky V. The application of plasma tart rate-acid resistant acid phosphatase to assess changes in bone re- sorption in response to artificial menopause and its treatment with estrogen norethisterone. *Calcif Tissue Int* 1989; 45:273-280.
6. Ettinger B, Genant HK, Cann CE. Long-term estrogen replacement therapy prevents bone loss and fractures. *Ann Intern Med* 1985; 102:319—324.
7. Ettinger B, Genant HK, Cann CE. Postmenopausal bone loss is prevented by treatment with low dosage estrogen with calcium *Ann Intern Med* 1987; 106:40—46.

8. Lindsay R. Estrogen therapy in the prevention and management of osteoporosis. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 1987; 156:1347-1351.
9. Riggs BL. Pathogenesis of osteoporosis. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 1987;156: 1342-1346?
10. Christiansen C, Christiansen MS, Transbfl I. Bone mass in postmenopausal women after withdrawal of estrogen progestogen replacement therapy. *Lancet* 1981; i:459-461.
11. Genant HK, Cann CE. Clinical impact of quantitative computer tomography for vertebral mineral assessment. *Diagnostic Radiology* 26th postgraduate course. Edited by AR Margulis. CA Gooding. San Francisco, University of California 1983:445—458.
12. Lindsay R, Hart DM, Clark DM. The minimum effective dose of estrogen for prevention of postmenopausal bone loss. *Obstet Gynecol* 1984; 63:759-763.
13. Nordin BEC, Smith DA. Laboratory procedures, diagnostic procedures in disorders of calcium metabolism, 1st edn. London: Churchill, 1965.
14. Heaney RP, Recker RR, Saville RP. Menopausal changes in bone remodeling. *I Lab Clin Med* 1978; 92:964—970.
15. Lindsay R. Estrogens in prevention and treatment of osteoporosis. *Schweiz Med Wochenschr* 1989; 119:1806—1810.
16. Cutler WB, Garcia C. The medical management of menopause and premenopause. Philadelphia: JB Lippincott Comp., 1984.
17. Ettinger B. Prevention of osteoporosis: treatment of estradiol deficiency. *Obstet Gynecol.* 1988; 72:12- 17 (suppl).
18. Lindsay R, Hart DM, Purdie D, Ferguson MH, Clark AS, Kraszewski A. Oestrogen and progestogen on bone loss in postmenopausal women. *Clin Sci Mol Med* 1978; 54:193- 195.
19. Christiansen C, Riis BJ, Nilas I, Rsdbro P, Deftos L. Uncoupling of bone formation and resorption by combined oestrogen and progestogen therapy in postmenopausal osteoporosis. *Lancet* 1985; ii:800-801.
20. Riis BJ, Johansen J, Christiansen C. Continuous oestrogen-progestogen treatment and bone metabolism of postmenopausal women. *Maturitas* 1988; 10:51—58.
21. Hirvonen E, Elliesen I, Schmidh-Gollwitzer K. Comparison of two hormone replacement regimens. Influence on lipoproteins and bone mineral content. *Maturitas* 1990; 12:127—136.
22. Riis BJ, Christiansen C. Prevention of postmenopausal bone loss: effects of alternative administration forms of estrogens, alternative gestagens and calcium addition. *NUC Compact.* 1987; 18:24-28.
23. Christiansen MS, Hagen C, Christiansen C, Transbal L. Dose-response evaluation of cyclic estrogen/gestagen in postmenopausal women: placebo-controlled trial of its gynecologic and metabolic actions. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 1982; 144:873—879
24. Riis BJ, Thomsen K, Strgm V, Christiansen C. The effect of percutaneous estradiol and natural progesterone on postmenopausal bone loss. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 1987; 156:61—65.
25. Christiansen C. Postmenopausal treatment with percutaneous estradiol. In: Dusitsin N, Notelovitz M, eds. *Physiological hormone replacement therapy.* Carnforth: Parthenon publishing group. 1991:51—59.
26. Stevenson JC, Cust MP, Gangar KF, Hillard TC, Lees B, Whitehead MI. Effects of transdermal versus oral hormone replacement therapy on bone density in spine and proximal femur in

postmenopausal women. Lancet 1990;
i:265—269.
27. Christiansen D, Christensen MS,
McNair P, Hagen C, Transbfl I.

Prevention of early postmenopausal
bone loss: controlled 2-year study in
315 normal females. Eur J Clin Invest
1980; 10:273-279.